

Assessment of attitude of parents towards the girl child education & early marriage at selected Rural community, west bengal

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Abstract:

The present study was aimed at assessing attitude of parents towards the girl child education and early marriage. The study analysed the data from 200 parents who had one or more than one unmarried girl children under the age of 18 years. The age of parents ranged from 25-40 years and they all belonged to Baruipur and Sonarpur block. Two tools (structured questionnaire) were constructed containing 20-items each for collecting data related to attitude of parents towards girl child education and early marriage and one tool was constructed for collecting demographic data. The respondents were required to indicate their agreement or disagreement with each of the statements about girl child education and early marriage in a five-point Likert scale, where 1 denotes strong disagreement and 5 denotes strong agreement positive question and the reverse scoring is for negative questions. Mean, Median and Standard Deviation were calculated for both attitude of parents towards girl child education and early marriage. The association between the attitude of parents towards girl child education and early marriage with selected demographic variables were calculated. Chi square test was used to determine the significance between the attitude of parents towards girl child education and early marriage. The findings showed that the overall attitude of the respondents was favourable attitude towards girl child education and also mostly they disagree with the early marriage.

Keywords:

Girl child education, Early Marriage, Rural Community, Median and Standard Deviation etc.

1. Introduction:

At the time of Independence, India's education system was characterized by regional, gender, caste and structural imbalances. At that time the literacy rate was only 14 % and only one in every three children were enrolled in primary schools.¹ Education plays a most significant role for changing the women's subjugated position in the society. It not only develops the personality and rationality of an